

THE IMPORTANCE OF MOTIVATION IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. This article is about the role of motivation in education and its influence on learning process of students. In order to clarify the importance of motivation, an experiment has been conducted on twenty pupils and this experiment gave a good and expected result. The experiment lasted for two months and twenty school children were worked on and observed individually.

Key words. Motivation, concentrating, psychology of students, responsibility, apathy, control work

Introduction. In this modern world, all fields of life has been developing and these changes are also showing their effect on education. We can see development in technologies, methods, techniques, and even knowledge of teachers and learners. However, motivation still remains paramount. Motivation is an inner force that inspires a person, motivates him or her to do something. It is important not only in education but also in other areas, because it affects the psychological aspects of a person. In order for people to succeed in any field, they must be psychologically stable and self-motivated enough. Palmer (2007) review the “student motivation is an essential element that is necessary for quality education. How do we know when students are motivated? They pay attention, they begin working on tasks immediately, they ask questions and volunteer answers, and they appear to be happy and eager”[5,1-23].

So many scientists have been tried to solve the problem of learners who are very slow in learning and have some difficulties in concentrating. At the end, most of researchers came to the conclusion that the only and effective solution is motivation.

An English language teacher also tried carrying out an experiment on children in order to define the role of giving a motivation. First of all, she determined the duration of experiment and formed a group of students. This group consisted of twenty children [4, 375-392].

Firstly, she observed every child individually and analyzed the psychology of each student deeply for two weeks. Among the pupils, one girl took her attention, because she was very calm and different. She does not speak to anyone and describe her thoughts fluently. Besides that, she is not interested in the subject and she does not do any homework given by teacher. Teacher gave her some warnings and punishments for her apathy. As a result, that girl began to hate her teacher and did not understand teacher's speech even in her own native language [1, 1438-1443]. Then she got used to missing classes and, as a result, she could not understand so many rules of the language which they are learning. After about four weeks passed, teacher took a control work from her pupils. Nearly, every student's results were excellent, but the result of the girl, who we have mentioned above, was very bad. Looking through her work, teacher found a lot of mistakes in her work. Nevertheless, teacher did not pay attention and did not check her work at all. She put just an excellent mark. The next lesson, teacher came into the classroom and said to her children "My dears, I am so happy from your results. You all are good, you are perfect. But among you only this girl took an excellent mark. Her work is the most worthwhile and I have not found any mistakes from it". Then she asked the girl to come next to the blackboard and commended for her result. After that, teacher asked the other student to applaud her. The girl was really shocked and so happy. Teacher said to her "As you see, you are the most intelligent student in this group and from today you will be responsible for other students' learning process".

Teacher did not change the style and techniques of teaching, she changed just her attitude towards that girl. But the result was amazing, because the girl began to understand the topic and express her feelings fluently. She get used to not only doing homework given by teacher, but also adding extra works independently.

As a conclusion, we can see that the role of motivation is very important in education. Sometimes it can be the only way to apply in order to make the situation better. Student motivation is an important element necessary for quality education. If students are motivated, then they begin to learn something, try to get useful information. As well as responsibility is also good way to make students motivated[2, 99-120].

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